

ANALYSIS OF THE PHYSIOLOGICAL MOBILITY OF TEETH IN VARIOUS AGE GROUPS

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ABSTRACT

The article presents a comparative analysis of the physiological state periodontium in different age groups. State characteristics are given support-retaining structures of teeth of various anatomical groups, age-related morphological and functional changes in various structures of the periodontium. Findings from Clinical Studies on Mobility teeth of various anatomical groups allow us to express an opinion about the presence of age-related features in the state of the periodontium without pronounced manifestations of the destructive-inflammatory process, and also allows more qualitatively select the number of abutment teeth in bridge and clasp prosthetics.

Keywords: periodontium, tooth mobility, age-related changes, aging.

The aging process is studied by the science of gerontology, which not only explores physiological changes, but also the place of the elderly age in society. The goal of gerontology research is to understand causes of aging and finding ways to combat it. Physiological changes that occur in the human body with age, are primarily expressed in a decrease in biological functions and adaptability to metabolic stress. These physiological changes are usually accompanied by psychological and behavioral changes. The actual biological aspects of aging include not only changes caused by aging, but also the deterioration of the general condition health. A person at a later age is more vulnerable to diseases, many of which are associated with a decrease in the effectiveness of the immune systems in old age. The so-called diseases of old age are thus a combination of the symptoms of aging, and diseases against which the body is no longer able to fight.

Aging is an inevitable physiological process due to complex changes in the molecular, cellular, tissue, organ and system levels. Distinguish between physiological and premature aging. Differences between physiological and premature aging is determined primarily by the number and degree the severity of age-related changes, as well as the possibilities compensatory-adaptive mechanisms, which are sharply reduced with premature aging [1]. The tissues that make up the periodontium have significant differences in structure and mechanical properties, which change with age, as well as under the influence of adverse environmental factors and previous diseases [2]. Morphofunctional changes in tissue structures and reduction adaptive capabilities are determined by age-related regulatory metabolic shifts in the metabolic processes of the dentition

[3, 4]. Over the years, the mass of the main substance increases in a person periodontal connective tissue, the number of cell structures, the content of fibrillar structures increases, their fibrosis and sclerosis with accumulation of neutral glycoproteins and the disappearance of hyaluronic acid, which is the reason for the decrease endurance periodontium to the load [4]. Progressive with age hypoxia of periodontal tissues causes coarsening of fibrous structures, their growth and accumulation of mucopolysaccharides. Decreased metabolism, reduction of vascularization and osteoporotic process contributes to atrophy of the bone tissue of the alveolar process [5]. Fibrofatty degeneration of the bone marrow, proliferation of plastic fibers of the walls blood vessels of the periodontium, degeneration of the circular ligament and disruption of its connection with the cementum accompany the aging process of the periodontium [6-8]. For assessment of periodontal status when examining a patient along with visual assessment, probing, determining the level of hygiene oral cavity and X-ray examination traditionally determination of tooth mobility is used [9, 10].

Purpose of the study. Determination of the functional state of the periodontium by measuring its resistance to horizontal loads and comparison of indicators in the examined different age groups.

Materials and methods. For the purpose of the survey, groups were formed persons with intact periodontium (IP) and defects in the dentition in the amount 146 people. According to the state of the dentition, the patients were distributed as follows: out of 47 patients in the age group of 20-39 years, one (2.12%) of the patient had an end defect of the dentition caused by absence of premolars and molars. End defects caused by absence

of molars were diagnosed in 2 (4.25%) patients. The majority of patients in this group had included defects in the lateral sections of the dentition of small length, caused by the absence of one or two adjacent teeth in 21 people (44.68%), and in 13 people (27.65%) included posterior dentition defects were caused by the absence of three or more teeth. Defects in the anterior dentition caused by the absence of one or two teeth, diagnosed in 7 (14.89%) patients, and only 3 (6.38%) patients had defects in the anterior dentition were caused by the absence of three or four teeth. In the age group of patients 40-59 years old, included defects in the dentition of different localization and extent were noted in 37 examined (71.15%) out of 52 people, and end defects - in 15 (28.85%). Among of the examined persons aged 60-75 years, end defects prevailed dental rows. They were detected in 26 people (70.27%) out of 37, while the included defects of the lateral and frontal sections of the dentition were diagnosed only in 11 patients (29.73%).

In the course of the research, measurements were made of the amplitude of scissions teeth of various anatomical groups: incisors, canines, premolars and molars. The oscillation amplitude was recorded in millimeters from the extreme vestibular to the extreme oral position of the examined tooth.

Research results. Physiological mobility of teeth in patients with intact periodontium undergoes age-related changes and significantly different in young, middle and old age. Persons young age (20-39 years) with IP, the amplitude of fluctuations of intact incisors, premolars and molars reaches 0.5 mm; fangs - 0.43-0.47 mm. In the middle age group (40-59 years), the amplitude of incisor oscillations, premolars and molars, other things being equal, has an average value 0.78 mm, and for fangs - 0.71 mm, which exceeds that of patients aged 20-39 years by 1.6-1.7 times.

Even in the absence inflammatory-destructive process, tooth mobility increases by 37-56%. When measuring tooth mobility in a group of people aged 60 years and older, the following data were obtained: incisors, premolars and molars in the subgroup without pronounced clinical and radiological signs of generalized periodontitis have an average value vibration amplitude 1.19 mm; canines - 1.0 mm. Results exceed similar indicators in the surveyed 20-39 years old by 2.3 times, and in persons 40-59 years old - 1.5 times. Based on the above, one can conclusion about the age-related decrease in the functional usefulness of the periodontium due to involutive changes. Analysis of the results of the study allows you to establish the following patterns: the mobility of the teeth of all functional groups in persons 20-39 years old with PV is within physiological norm and does not exceed 0.6 mm. In subjects aged 40-59 years with intact periodontium, the mobility of incisors, premolars and molars averaged 0.78 mm, and canines - 0.71 mm, which can be consider it a conditional physiological norm for this age group; c the same time for people over 60 relative the physiological norm averages 1.2 mm. Results clinical studies of tooth mobility of various anatomical groups allow us to express

an opinion about the presence of age-related features in condition of the periodontium without pronounced manifestations of destructive inflammatory process. The age of the patient is essential adjust drug treatment regimens, introduce into them osteogenesis stimulants and vitamin- ineral complexes. The effectiveness of treatment and the length of the intervals between therapeutic complexes also depends on age. It is necessary to take into account the age characteristics of the state of the periodontium and choosing the design of the prosthesis, in particular - in planning the number supporting teeth for a bridge or clasp prosthesis.

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